

IMPROVING THE QUALITY OF LIFE OF THE POPULATION THROUGH THE DEVELOPMENT OF PRIVATE ENTREPRENEURSHIP

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Annotatation. The article defines the concept of poverty, describes the conditions, principles, foreign experience and ways to effectively use it, the importance of small business and private entrepreneurship in reducing poverty in the region.

Keywords: Poverty, poverty reduction, poverty level, unemployment, destitution.

Introduction. Today, according to the World Bank, 736 million people on our planet live in extreme poverty. The UN defines the poverty line as the income needed to buy basic goods and services (food, clothing, housing, water, electricity, schooling, and health care). Poverty is a relative concept and depends on the general level of well-being in a particular country. Economist Dinitto notes that there are five different approaches to defining and understanding poverty in the United States. These are: poverty in the form of deprivation of means of livelihood, poverty in the form of inequality, poverty in the form of culture, poverty in the form of exploitation, and poverty in the form of structure.

The standard of living of the population, as a measure of the satisfaction of people's vital needs, reflects the quantity and quality of consumption and is constantly improving. So, what does this consumption, that is, the satisfaction of people's needs, depend on, and based on it, can we draw conclusions about the level of people's standard of living and the level of well-being of their lives? The standard of living of people depends on the level of development of production in a given society. Because consumption is a product of production. Here, the ratio of national income to savings and consumption funds depends on the state of economic development of the country. For this reason, the standard of living of the population is a broad process that depends on various factors (from the region where the population lives, that is, the geographical factor, to the general socio-economic and ecological situation in the country, as well as the state of political affairs). The standard of living of the population can be influenced to a greater or lesser extent by

the demographic situation, as well as by housing and working conditions, as well as by the volume and quality of consumer goods. Based on the results of our research, we consider it appropriate to divide the standard of living of the population into four groups based on poverty reduction:

Research has shown that a number of indicators have been included in the system of basic indicators characterizing the standard of living of the population in economic literature. The latest version of the UN system of indicators of standard of living in the field of international statistics was developed in 1978, and this system includes 12 main groups. These are: gross domestic product per capita, birth, death, life expectancy, availability of sanitary and hygienic conditions, level of food consumption, housing conditions, availability of educational and cultural opportunities, working conditions and level of employment, balance of income and expenditure, consumer prices, means of transport, etc. The availability of food, the availability of opportunities for rest and recreation, the availability of a social security system, and the guarantee of human rights and freedoms are considered indicators of the standard of living.

As a result of monographic observations, it became clear that in the Republic of Uzbekistan in recent years, a number of practical measures have been taken to develop private entrepreneurship in order to reduce poverty and prevent poverty, and positive indicators have been achieved Figure 1.

In particular:

Legal rights were introduced for private business entities, and a system was formed to increase their personal interests and protect their interests;

Figure 1: Standard of living of the population.

a system of guarantees of freedom of private enterprise was formed;

a simplified, digitized procedure for state registration and accounting of private business entities was introduced;

favorable conditions and opportunities were created for private business entities to freely purchase material and technical resources through stock exchanges;

Compulsory standardization and certification of products of enterprises producing goods and services was simplified;

measures were taken to reduce and simplify the tax burden; a shortened form of statistics and tax reporting was introduced.

Conclusion and Recommendations. In order to effectively solve these problems in the field of private entrepreneurship development in order to reduce poverty, it is necessary to develop and implement strategic programs of the government of the republic aimed at supporting this. On the basis of such a concept,

it is possible to eliminate inequalities and more effectively use the economic potential of the regions. It is expedient.

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